

Automated Identification of Self-Admitted Technical Debt in Source Code with Machine Learning SBES 2024

Este documento complementar é disponibilizado em conjunto com o artigo intitulado "Automated Identification of Self-Admitted Technical Debt in Source Code with Machine Learning". Ele abrange os resultados obtidos na Revisão Rápida. Caso tenha alguma dúvida específica ou precise de esclarecimentos sobre o conteúdo do documento, por favor, sinta-se à vontade para compartilhar mais detalhes ou fazer perguntas específicas. Estamos à disposição para ajudar!

Na Tabela C1 pode ser observado as 33 publicações selecionadas após o segundo filtro conforme estabelecido no protocolo da Revisão Rápida.

Tabela C2 – Lista dos artigos selecionados

ID	Artigo	Autor(es)	Ano	Fonte de Publicação
P01	A Systematic Literature Review on Technical Debt Prioritization: Strategies, Processes, Factors and Tools	Lenarduzzi, V, Besker, T, Taibi, D, Martine, A e Fontana F	2021	Journal of Systems and Software
P02	Analisando Estratégias de Identificação de Dívidas Técnicas	Oliveira, I; Neto, H e Xavier, L	2020	Workshop de Visualização, Evolução e Manutenção de Software
P03	An Empirical Study on Self-Admitted Technical Debt in Dockerfiles	Azuma, H; Matsumoto, S; Kamei, Y e Kusumoto, S	2022	Empirical Software Engineering
P04	An Empirical Study on the Co-Occurrence Between Refactoring Actions and Self-Admitted Technical Debt Removal	Iammoarino, M; Zampetti, F; Aversano, L e Penta, M	2021	Journal of Systems and Software
P05	An Overview and Comparison of Technical Debt Measurement Tools	Avgeriou, P; Taibi, D; Ampatzoglou, A; Fontana, F; Besker, T; Chatzigeorgiou, A; Lenarduzzi, V; Martini, A; Moschou, A; Pigazzini, I; Saarimaki, N; Sas, D; Toledo, S e Tsintzira, A	2021	IEEE Software
P06	Architectural Technical Debt in Microservices	Toledo, S; Martini, A; Przybyszewska, A e Sjøberg, D	2019	International Conference on Technical Debt
P07	ATDx: Building an Architectural Technical Debt Index	Verdecchia, R; Lago, P; Malavolta, I e Ozkaya, I.	2020	International Conference on Evaluation of Novel Approaches to Software Engineering
P08	Automating Change-Level Self-Admitted Technical Debt Determination	Yan, M; Xia, X; Shihab, E; Lo, D; Yin, J e Yang, X	2018	IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering
P09	A Tertiary Study on Technical Debt: Types, Management Strategies, Research Trends, and base Information for Practitioners	Rios, N; Neto, M e Spínola, R	2018	Information and Software Technology
P10	Common Causes and Effects of Technical Debt in Serbian IT: InsignTD Survey Replication	Ramač, R; Mandić, V; Taušan, N; Rios, N; Neto, M; Seaman, C e Spínola, R	2020	Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications

P11	Conceptualisation of Using Technical Debt 2 to Measure the Innovation Level of New Product – 3 Selected Issues	Filipowicz, P	2021	Scientific Papers of Silesian University of Technology
P12	Embracing Technical Debt, from a Startup Company Perspective	Besker, T; Martini, A; Lokuge, R; Blincoe, K e Bosch, J	2018	International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution
P13	Familiarity, Causes and Reactions of Software Practitioners to the Presence of Technical Debt: A Replicated Study in the Chilean Software Industry	Pérez, B; Brito, J; Astudillo, H; Correal, D; Rios, N; Spínola, R; Mendonça, M e Seaman, C	2019	International Conference of the Chilean Computer Science Society
P14	How do Developers Fix Issues and Pay Back Technical Debt in the Apache Ecosystem?	Digkas, G; Lungu, M; Avgeriou, P; Chatzigeorgiou, A e Ampatzoglou, A	2018	International Conference on Software Analysis, Evolution and Reengineering
P15	Identifying Design and Requirement Self-Admitted Technical Debt using N-gram IDF	Wattanakriengkra, S; Maipradit, R; Hata, H; Choetkiertikul, M; Sunetnanta, T e Matdumoto, K	2018	International Workshop on Empirical Software Engineering in Practice
P16	Increasing Awareness for Potential Technical Debt in the Engineering of Production Systems	Ocker, F; Seitz, M; Oligschläger, M; Zou, M e Heuser, B.	2019	International Conference on Industrial Informatics
P17	Introducing the Concept of Technical Debt to Smart Grids: A System Engineering Perspective	Schütz, J e Uslar, M.	2019	International Conference and Exhibition on Electricity Distribution
P18	Investigating the Point of View of Project Management Practitioners on Technical Debt - A Study on Stack Exchange	Gomes, F; Santos, E; Freire, S; Mendonça, M; Mendes, T e Spínola, R	2022	In Proceedings of the International Conference on Technical Debt
P19	Managing Architectural Technical Debt: A Unified Model and Systematic Literature Review	Besker, T; Martini, A e Bosch, J	2018	Journal of Systems and Software
P20	Preventing Technical Debt with the TAP Framework for Technical Debt Aware Management	Wiese, M; Rachow, P; Riebisch, M e Schwarze, J	2022	Information and Software Technology
P21	Security Risk Assessment and Management as Technical Debt	Rindell, K e Holvitie J	2019	International Conference on Cyber Security and Protection of Digital Services
P22	Technical Debt and Agile Software Development Practices and Processes: An Industry Practitioner Survey	Holvitie, J; Licorish, S; Spínola, R; Hyrybsalmi, S; MacDonell, S; Mendes, T; Buchan, J e Leppänen, V	2018	Information and Software Technology
P23	Technical Debt Aware Estimations in Software Engineering: A Systematic Mapping Study	Klimczyk, P e Madeyski, L	2020	e-Informatica Software Engineering Journal
P24	Technical Debt in Hardware Systems and Elements	Rosser, L e Ouzzif, Z	2021	IEEE Aerospace Conference
P25	Technical Debt in Large-Scale Distributed Projects: An Industrial Case Study	Sousa, A; Rocha, L; Britto, R; Gong, Z e Lyu F	2021	International Conference on Software Analysis,

				Evolution and Reengineering
P26	Technical Debt Management Automation: State of the Art and Future Perspectives	Biazotto, J; Feitosa, D; Avgeriou, P e Nakagawa, E	2023	Information and Software Technology
P27	Technical Debt Prioritization: Taxonomy, Methods Results and Practical Characteristics	Pina, D; Goldaman, A e Tonin, G	2021	Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications
P28	Technical Debt Tracking: Current State of practice: A Survey and Multiple Case Study in 15 Large Organizations	Martini, A, Besker, T e Bosch, J	2018	Science of Computer Programming
P29	The Lifecycle of Technical Debt that Manifests in Both Source Code and Issue Trackers	Tan, J; Feitosa, D e Avgeriou, P	2023	Information and Software Technology
P30	The Role of Awareness and Gamification on Technical Debt Management	Crespo, Y; Nozal, C; Sánchez, R; Tasis, M e Piattini, M	2022	Information and Software Technology
P31	Toward a Technical Debt Conceptualization for Serverless Computing	Lenarduzzi, V; Daly, J; Martini, A; Panichella, S e Tamburri	2021	IEEE Software
P32	Uma Análise da Relação entre Code Smells e Dívida Técnica Auto-Admitida	Gomes, F; Mendes, T; Spínola, R; Mendonça, M e Farias, M	2019	Workshop de Visualização, Evolução e Manutenção de Software
P33	Who (Self) Admits Technical Debt?	Fucci, G; Zampetti, F; Serebrenik, A e Penta, M	2020	International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution

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